

Aliphatic Compounds from *Melastoma melabathricum*

B. DINDA* and M. K. SAHA

Department of Chemistry, Calcutta University Post Graduate Centre, Agartala-799 004

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Two new aliphatic compounds, 1-octyl docosanoate and 11-methyl-1-tritriacontanol have been isolated from the aerial parts of *Melastoma melabathricum* and characterised on the basis of chemical and spectroscopic evidences.

MELASTOMA melabathricum L.¹ of family *Melastomataceae* is a shrub of variable heights (3–8 ft) found in the hilly areas as well as in the lower level lands of Tripura, Assam and Bangladesh. It is cultivated as a garden plant. The leaves, flowers and fruits are edible. The plant is said to be useful in the treatment of cholera, diarrhoea, prolonged fever, dysentery, leucorrhoea, wounds, skin diseases and for the preparation of gargles². Previous investigations¹⁻³ on the roots reported the presence of a purple dyestuff, β -sitosterol and melastomic acid. We investigated the aerial parts of the plant and isolated two new aliphatic compounds, a long-chain ester and a longchain alcohol.

Results and Discussion

From the petrol extract of the aerial parts of *M. melabathricum*, two crystalline compounds A and B were isolated by silica gel chromatography.

Compound A was obtained as colourless crystals after repeated crystallisation from petrol, m.p. 89°. Elemental analyses and mass spectral study (M^+ 452) suggest the compound A to be $C_{30}H_{60}O_2$. It exhibited ir absorption band at 1740 cm^{-1} showing the presence of a saturated ester function in the molecule. The ^1H nmr spectrum of the compound displayed signals for 2 methyl groups at δ 0.88 (6H, t, J 6.5 Hz) and 25 methylene groups at δ 1.24 (50H, br s). The appearance of a two-proton triplet centered at δ 2.28 (J 7.0 Hz) suggested the presence of one methylene group α to the ester carbonyl function. A two-proton triplet at δ 4.05 (J 6.5 Hz) was indicative of one methylene group attached to ester oxygen ($\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{CO}-$). On the basis of ir and ^1H nmr studies it was concluded that the compound was a longchain saturated aliphatic ester. The precise nature of the structure of the compound was largely elicited from its mass spectrum. Besides the molecular ion peak, the spectrum showed significant peaks at m/z 409, 323, 295, 185, 172, 157 and 129 together with many peaks with uniform loss of 14 mu which can best be rationalised⁴⁻⁶ (Scheme 1) in terms of 1-octyl docosanoate structure (1) for the compound A. This is also supported by the fact that saponification of compound A (see experimental) gave 1-octanol and a longchain aliphatic

Scheme 1

acid, $C_{22}H_{44}O_2$ (M^+ 340), m.p. 78°; the physical constants as well as spectral data of which compare excellently with those of docosanoic acid (2) (behenic acid⁷). All the foregoing evidence thus suggest the structure (1) for compound A.

Compound B was crystallised from petrol, m.p. 93°. It was analysed as $C_{34}H_{70}O$ from its elemental analyses and molecular ion peak at m/z 494. The ir spectrum of the compound showed a band at $3400-3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting the presence of a hydroxyl group in the molecule. The presence of hydroxyl group was also confirmed by preparation of its acetate, $C_{36}H_{72}O_2$, m.p. 76°. Compound B is a saturated aliphatic alcohol as its molecular formula corresponds the general formula $C_nH_{2n+2}O$ for a saturated aliphatic alcohol. The ^1H nmr spectrum of the compound displayed two methyl signals at δ 0.84 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz) and 0.88 (3H, t, J 6.5 Hz) which were assigned to a terminal methyl and a methyl attached to a carbon atom of the long methylene chain. A one proton signal at

δ 1.65 (m) was assigned to a methine proton in the methylene chain. The spectrum also showed signals at δ 3.65 (2H, t, J 6.5 Hz), 1.5 (2H, s) and 1.24 (58H, br s) which can be attributed to the grouping, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-$ and 29 methylene groups in the molecule. The mass spectrum is more significant to ascertain the methylene chain of the molecule. It showed a series of intense peak at m/z 476 [$M-18$], 448 [$M-46=M-(\text{H}_2\text{O}+\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}_2)$], 420, 392, 364, ..., which followed the sequence [$M-(18+n \cdot 28)$], n being 1, 2, 3, 4, ..., a typical feature⁸ for longchain alcohol. Moreover, the appearance of another two series of peaks at m/z 41, 55, 69, 13, ... and 43, 57, 71, 85, .. the relative abundance decreasing with increasing fragment mass clearly suggested a long methylene chain⁶ of the molecule. But appearance of intense peak at m/z 307 [$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{44}$] after gradual decrease in the relative abundance in the series [$\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}-(\text{CH}_2)_n$]⁺, n being 1, 2, 3, etc. suggested the presence of branch methyl on C_{11} -carbon. The position of branch methyl on C_{11} -carbon on compound B was also supported by the mass spectrum of its acetate (4), which showed two intense peaks at m/z 227 [$M-\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{44}$] and 167 [$227-\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{H}$]. All the foregoing facts may be explained in terms of structure (3) for compound B (Scheme 1). Thus, compound B is 11-methyl-1-tritriacontanol (3).

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 at 100 MHz with TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL FX 100 spectrometer. Tlc was carried out on silica gel G and spots were located with I_2 -vapour. Petrol used had b.p. 60–80°. All analytical samples were tested for purity by tlc.

Collection the aerial part of the plant⁹ *Melastoma melabathricum* L. was collected (May, 1984) from the hilly areas of Agartala in the State of Tripura.

Extraction and isolation: The plant material was dressed into small chips, air-dried and ground to a coarse powder. Powdered plant material was exhaustively extracted with petrol in Soxhelt for 48 h. The extract was concentrated and chromatographed over silica gel, the column being eluted with solvents of increasing polarity starting with petrol. The process of elution was monitored by tlc of 100 ml fractions. Chromatographically similar fractions were combined and solvent removed by evaporation on a steam-bath.

Compound A [1-octyl docosanoate (1)]: Fractions (3, 4) of petrol eluate, after recrystallisation from petrol yielded colourless crystals of compound A (60 mg) m.p. 89° (Found: C, 79.20; H, 12.82. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{60}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 79.58; H, 13.36%); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 920, 2 840, 2 340, 1 740, 1 475, 1 465, 1 185 and 1 175 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.88 (6H, t, J 6.5 Hz, 2Me), 1.24 (50H, s, 25 CH_2), 2.28 (2H, t, J 7.0 Hz, $\text{CH}_2-\text{CO}-\text{O}$) and 4.05 (2H, t, J 6.5 Hz, $\text{CO}-\text{O}-$

CH_2); m/z (rel. int.) 452 [M^+] (0.2), 437 [$M-\text{Me}$] (0.4), 409 [$M-43$] (0.2), 339 [$M-\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17}$] (7.5), 323 [$M-\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17}\text{O}$] (5.6), 295 (3.7), 267 (1.5), 239(1.8), 211(2.0), 197(2.0), 185(3.0), 183(2.5), 172(2.8), 169 (5.0), 157(3.0), 155(10.0), 141(24.2), 129(13.5), 127(8.5), 113(11.2), 99(19.5), 85(74.5), 71(97.8), 60(27.5), 59(5.0), 57(100) and 43(99.8).

Saponification of compound A (1): 1 (25 mg) was refluxed with 1N MeOH-KOH (5 ml) on a steam-bath for 3 h in an atmosphere of N_2 . The residue after removal of MeOH under reduced pressure was diluted with H_2O , extracted with cold ether, dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated on a steam-bath to give 1-octanol (5 mg) (ms was identical with reported data⁶).

The aqueous layer after ether-extraction was acidified with 4 N aqueous HCl and extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried and evaporated when a glassy residue (10 mg) of docosanoic acid (2) was obtained, m.p. 78° (lit.⁷ 80°) (Found: C, 76.85; H, 12.20. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 77.58; H, 13.02%); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 920, 2 850, 1 705, (C=O), 1 460, 1 310 and 1 295, 1 280, 1 260, 1 235, 1 220, 1 205 and 1 190 (characteristic of longchain n-alkyl compound in a solid state)¹⁰ and 730 and 720 cm^{-1} ; m/z (rel. int.) 340 [M^+] (0.3), 323(0.1), 297(0.1), 295(0.1), 267(0.3), 239(0.3), 211(0.6), 183(1.7), 169(3.8), 155(6.5), 141(14.0), 127(12.8), 113(43.0), 99(15.0), 85(56.4), 71(99.7), 60(48.0), 57(100.0, base peak), 45(71.5), 43(99.8) and 17(90.3).

Compound B [11-methyl-1-tritriacontanol (3)]: It was obtained from fractions (6–9) of petrol eluate, as colourless light granular crystals after several recrystallisations from petrol (80 mg), m.p. 93° (Found: C, 81.92; H, 13.65. $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{70}\text{O}$ calcd. for: C, 82.51, H, 14.26%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} +0.6$ (c 0.9 in CHCl_3); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400–3 210 (OH), 2 920, 2 850, 1 470, 1 460, 1 060, 730 and 720 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.84 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz, 1Me), 0.88 (3H, t, J 6.5 Hz, 1Me), 5.25 (1H, diffuse t, OH)⁶, 1.24 (58H, s, 29 CH_2), 1.50 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}$), 1.65 (1H, m, ($\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)$)) and 3.65 (2H, t, J 6.5 Hz, CH_2-O); m/z (rel. int.) 494 [M^+] (0.1), 493 [$M-1$] (0.3), 492 [$M-2$] (0.5), 476 [$M-18$] (5.7), 448 [$M-46$] (11.3), 420(4.8), 392(7.3), 364(4.2), 336(3.6), 309(1.5), 308(3.2), 307(3.5), 280(3.0), 253(2.0), 251(5.3), 239(2.5), 237(5.3), 225(3.2), 223(11.6), 211(4.2), 209(8.5), 197(5.3), 195(10.6), 183(6.4), 181(13.7), 169(10.8), 167(22.3), 155(17.0), 153(28.6), 141(35.0), 139(40.2), 127(20.0), 125(62.5), 113(24.4), 111(75.0), 99(37.1), 97(95.0), 85(78.4), 83(97.0), 71(89.0), 69(97.5), 57(99.8), 55(99.0), 43(100.0, base peak), 41(92.2).

Acetate (4) of compound B: Compound B (20 mg) was acetylated with Ac_2O and pyridine and the acetylated product was worked up in the usual manner and the residue was chromatographed to give shining crystals of the acetate from petrol eluate (10 mg), m.p. 76° (Found: C, 79.90; H, 12.82. $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{72}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: C, 80.52; H, 13.50%); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 920, 2 850, 1 740 (C=O), 1 470, 1 460, 1 365, 1 245, 1 045, 730 and 720 cm^{-1} ; m/z (rel. int.)

227(4.3), 167(4.9), 141(8.5), 139(4.9), 85(9.8), 83(26.8), 57(85.6), 43(100.0) and 41(96.4).

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